

Literature Review on Training Needs Analysis

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Introduction

As competition has grown as a very dominant factor in all kinds of business sector, all business sectors have started introducing competent employees having realized the importance of competition in the business. At the same time, they have also understood that it is not only important recruiting competent for their business, it is also important to equip them to work competently and professionally. Hence, they focus their attention making their employees productive by improving their knowledge, skills and attitude not only to manage the organization smoothly and perfectly but also to face the competition successfully. Hence, it is essentially needed for all organizations to carry out training needs analysis to design appropriate training programme. This secondary data based research work has reviewed previous studies related to training needs analysis and presented definition, importance and previous studies related to training need analysis.

Objective

The objective of this research is to review the studies related to training needs analysis.

Definition

Needs assessment is a process for pinpointing reasons for gaps in performance or a method for identifying new and future performance needs (Gupta, 1999). It also diagnoses present problems and future challenges to be met through training and development (William B Werther and Keith Davis, 1993). It is also used as one form of an evaluation tool (Lee and Nelson, 2006). It is the starting point in the training process.

Therefore, it is defined that training needs analysis is an ongoing process of gathering data to determine what training needs exist so that training can be developed to help the organisation accomplish its objectives (Brown, 2002).

Importance of Training Needs Analysis

Training needs analysis is done to seek information about optimal performance or knowledge, actual or current performance or knowledge, feelings of trainees and other significant people, causes of the problems and solutions to the problem. Moreover, it helps to identify training needs at employee, departmental or organisational level in order to help the organisation to perform effectively (Rossett, 1987).

It is the phase in which an organization's needs are identified, forming the foundation of an effective training effort. The needs assessment tells where and what kind of training programs are needed, who needs to be included, conditions under which training will occur, and criteria to guide program evaluation. (Anderson, 2000; Sorenson, 2002).

A needs analysis is a wise investment for the organization when it is done properly and it also saves time, money and effort when it is done on the right problems. Failure to conduct a training needs assessment or conducting one ineffectively can lead to costly mistakes (McArdle, 1998).

Studies Related to Training Needs Analysis

Rajan D (2014) analysed training need of nurses with the objectives of analyzing training needs of the nurses by understanding their perception towards function and behaviour related factors. The results of the study proved that majority of the respondents were in need of training in terms of both behaviour and function related areas. Besides, inability to compete with seniors, not knowing about self motivation, inability to have positive attitude always, difficulty to tolerate criticism of co-workers, higher officers and patients, developing stress, difficulty to go flexible with co-workers, seniors and other supporting staffs, difficulty to manage office politics, difficulty to adopt frequent changing policies of the hospital and afraid to convey grievances to higher officers were strongly agreed by majority of the respondents in terms of behaviour related factors. Furthermore, having less knowledge about the way of utilizing the resources, not knowing how to exhibit the knowledge gained from subject and ability in the work, difficulty to divide the work and delegate, committing mistakes in the work processes, need of assistance to operate equipments and carryout treatment procedures, fear to deal with emotionally imbalanced patients, fear to deal with emergency and crisis situations, not knowing how to plan work and do it systematically, difficulty to take decision about the treatment of the patients when the doctor or senior nurse are not available in the department, fear and hesitation to speak to the doctors about patient's condition and clear the doubt, difficult to carry out the instructions of doctors and surgeons fast, difficulty to carryout multiple work at the same time were strongly agreed by majority of the respondents in terms of function related factors.

Santhosh Kumar (2013) analysed the level of knowledge of Tasmac employees about various kind of customers, elements of alcohols, way of monitoring the customers and when to stop or delay serving people, how to handle difficult customers, handling emergencies due to intoxication and ethical and social responsibility while serving alcohol. The study suggested that the bar attached restaurants can be eliminated and the bars can be operated as a retail outlet only. The training can be extended to a certification for managers and alcoholic service personals of private outlets also. Those who had hotel management graduation background should be recruited in order to monitor and serve the people better. Training should also emphasise how to create awareness to the customers about disadvantage of alcohol consumption.

Ramadevi and Mallika Rao (2012) in their study analysed the skills such as patient care, administrative duties, managerial or supervisory skills and clinical skills, planning and organizing skills, enthusiasm in learning, communication, personal bearing and team spirit. The result of the study showed that among the studied variable the training need gap is more for enthusiasm

in learning followed by team spirit and clinical skills. The training need gap is the least for communication followed by planning and organizing skills.

Almerich Gonzalo et al. (2011) analysed training needs of teachers in ICT: Training profiles and elements of complexity. The study aimed to establish teacher training profiles to help related them to their information and communication technologies competencies and use thereof together with personal and contextual factors. The study sampled 868 primary and secondary education teachers in the Valencian community (East Spain). The results indicated that teachers demanded higher level training in the personal professional area and that they required more training with students in class room and to integrate ICT into class rooms. The study indicated that these needs should be arranged into four profiles: initial, initial intermediate, intermediate and advanced. A clear relationship was also found between these training need profiles with ICT competencies especially technology, use of ICT mainly in the personal professional area. The study found that teacher's age and frequency of computers use were seen to also influence these profiles. The study recommended that educational administrations should consider these results when developing teacher training plans to produce higher quality programmes in accordance with demand from various fields.

Liaquat Hussain et al. (2011) analysed the previous knowledge of the University teachers regarding use of computer resources, needs of University teachers regarding use of computer resources and developed teachers with latest skills, method of teaching with respect to special educational needs which fulfil the needs of the students. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference between the mean pre test and post test score of the University teachers before and after the training regarding use of computer resources. The study recommended that all the teachers in different departments of the University should be trained in the use of computer. Team for in-service training programme must be organized and trained with innovative developments in the field of computer. The in-service teachers training programme should include the introduction about hardware and software, use of hardware specially the printer, scanner, flash, CD, multimedia and use of software. The content of the training must be flexible and they may be easily changed according to the changing needs of the teachers.

Michelle Beckman (2007) made a need assessment to determine whether training deficiencies exist and if so what objectives should be covered in order to develop the competencies that the warehouse employees need. The result found that there performance problem existed in the warehouse. The study recommended that in the depth survey should be made including more information about job satisfaction and training. The study also suggested that survey should be done by someone external to the organization and changes should be made in research practices such as choosing a different gap analysis method such as systems thinking.

Bello and Tijani (2006) analysed the training needs of teachers by examining their level of knowledge and difficulties encountered in the development and administration of different assessment. The research sampled 2422 teachers from junior secondary and senior secondary schools and 448 heads of schools and educational administrators or officers in Ghana, Nigeria and Gambia. The result showed that assessment tools like essay test, objective test and assignments were frequently used and found easy to score by teachers. Teachers were however found deficient in the use of other assessment tools particularly in the assessment of project work, formative testing, assessment by interviews and behavioural assessment. The teachers signified their ambition to be trained in these areas as well as in the development of marketing schemes or scoring keys.

Conclusion

This secondary data based work has reviewed various studies related to training needs analysis of various occupational groups and summarised the results.

References

1. Almerich Gonzalo., Suarez Rodriguez Jesus M., Belloch Consuelo and Rosa B.O. (2011). Training Needs of Teachers in ICT: Training Profiles and Elements of Complexity. E-Journal of Educational, Research, Assessment and Evaluation, Vol. 17, No. 2, pp, 1-27.
2. Anderson J. E. (2000). Training needs assessment, evaluation, success, and organizational strategy and effectiveness: An exploration of the relationships. (Doctoral Dissertation, Utah State University. Logan, UT).
3. Bello M. A. and Tijani A. A. (2006). Training Needs of Teachers in School Based Assessment in Anglophone West African Countries. Retrieved on 13-03-2014 from http://www.iaea.info/documents/paper_2fb24ab5.pdf.
4. Brown J. (2002). Training Needs Assessment: A Must for Developing an Effective Training Program, Public Personnel Management, Vol. 31, No. 4, pp. 569-578.
5. Deutsch A. (1979). The Human Resource Revolution: Communicate or Litigate, St Louis, NY, McGraw-Hill Book Co.
6. Gupta K. (1999). A Practical Guide to Needs Assessment. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass/Pfeiffer.
7. Lee Howard D. and Nelson Orville W. (2006) Instructional Analysis and Course Development. Homewood, IL: American Technical Publishers.
8. Liaquat Hussain, Umar Ali, Muhammad Abrar and Faridullah Shah. (2011). Training Needs Assessment of University Teachers Regarding Use of Computer Resources. Gomal University Journal of Research, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 135-142.
9. McArdle G. (1998). Conducting a Needs Analysis. Menlo Park, CA: Crisp Learning.
10. Michelle Beckman. (2007). Training Needs Assessment for Warehouse Employees. MS Project of University of Menomonie, WI, pp. 1-33.
11. Ramadevi V. and Mallika Rao M. (2012). Training Needs Identification of Nursing Staff-A Case Study of a Health Care Organization. Excel International Journal of Multi Disciplinary Management Studies, Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 147-153.
12. Rajan, D. (2014). Training Need Analysis: A Study of Nurses in Private Hospitals. Training and Development Journal, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 46-55.
13. Rossett A. (1987). Training Needs Assessment. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Educational Technology Publications.
14. Santhosh Kumar M. (2013). Training Needs Analysis for Tasmac Employees in Tamilnadu. Middle East Journal of Scientific Research, Vol. 17, No. 12, pp. 1802-1804.
15. Sorenson S. (2002). Training for the Long Run. Engineered Systems, pp. 32.
16. William B Werther and Keith Davis. (1993). Human Resources and Personnel Management, Fourth Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York, p. 309.